

Artificial Intelligence in Educational Foundations: A Technology Innovation Approach to Teaching and Learning in Public Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

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Abstract

This paper investigated the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Educational Foundations, focusing on technology-driven innovations for teaching and learning in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Adopting a descriptive research design, the study addressed four research questions and three null hypotheses. The population comprised 6,245 academic staff (4,723 male, 1,522 female) from three public universities: the University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State University, and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting 500 lecturers (300 male, 200 female), representing 10% of the population. Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire, titled: Artificial Intelligence in Educational Foundation Questionnaire (AIEFQ), The questionnaire consists of two sections, section A dealt with items on demographic data of the respondents such as names, age, sex, marital status, years, qualification, while section B dealt with the question's items in cluster of the independent variables. The response patterns were 4-point rating scale patterns as; Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The instrument was validated by experts and tested for reliability via test-retest. Responses were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and an independent t-test at a 0.05 significance level via SPSS version 24. Findings revealed that AI tools like automated grading systems, blended learning, and SPSS were extensively used in Educational Management. The study concluded that AI significantly enhanced students' performance in Educational Foundations in Rivers State's tertiary institutions. Recommendations included: appointing digitally competent management staff, providing adequate technological infrastructure, and ensuring widespread adoption of AI tools for administrative and academic functions across institutions.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Innovation, Educational Foundation, Approach, Technology, Teaching and Learning, Public Tertiary Institutions.

Introduction

Technology has become an important source of innovation and improvement of efficiency for many sectors across the globe. In the education sector, particularly, the application of Technology has become a critical part of the learning process for secondary students both outside and inside the classroom setting. According to Albin (2020), some stakeholders consider technology as effective learning facilitators and have invested huge amount of money to adopt technology in the education system during the last two decades. Some studies suggest that most secondary schools that have fully adopted technology into teaching-learning have recorded immense advancement in terms of learning outcome and improvement of teaching methods. It is, however, clear what effect the technological applications and integration have on the performance and achievement of students.

Integration of technology adoption in this study is understood as a gradual switching over to automation of the educational process not only in administrative activities like students' admission, registration, and evaluation but also developing a customized learning management system (LMS) and transferring all the subject and the related data onto it. The teachers as well as the students are allowed access to the LMS along with its all services and the specialized online learning tools. The adoption of technology in Nigerian schools has reportedly facilitated the educational processes to a great extent. However, there are varying opinions on the centrality of Technology in the learning processes in schools. For some, Technology is the thing in modern learning and failure to switch over to Technology -based learning is seen as failure in learning process enhancement. While some educationist view the traditional instruction method as retaining its core relevance irrespective of Technology innovations, others see the traditional method as outdated mode that needs to be enhanced through the adoption of Technology resources. According to Hamidi, Meshkat, Razaee and Jafari (2020) Technology are seen as central to the overall learning process rather it is adopted for the purpose of emphasis. According to them, even in the most advanced schools in advance countries, Technology are considered central to the teaching and learning process. They further noted that Technology in education initiatives in many less developed countries seek (at least in their rhetoric) to place technology as central to teaching and learning. Similarly, Capan (2019) stated that one of the enduring problems of the 21st century education planning is putting technology before education. According to him, educational planners and technology advocates should think of the technology first and then investigate the educational applications of this technology only later.

On the other hand, strong advocates of technology-based learning are of the view that the use of Technology makes learning easier for the learning and reduces the task of the teachers as illustrations can easily be made with the use of technology. According to Chien (2020), technology is a tool for effective instructions of weak learner, who through repetitive illustrations can comprehend what they may not be able to understand at first instance in the classroom. Furthermore, Albin (2020) noted that the use of technology makes learning less passive and more interactive hence, toning up the enthusiasm of learning and passionately bring them to the corridors of knowledge. For Gulbahar and Guven (2019), the adoption of technology use in teaching and learning improves students' academic performance. Students' academic performance is the results of students of learning. It also refers to the enhancement of the students' current state of knowledge and skills reflected in their result averages and also in the formulation of their personality and academic growth from lower levels of study to higher levels. The rationale of studying academic performance in the context of Technology adoption is to present a significant relationship that exists between the two variables.

The pro- technology scholars are generally of the view that Technology can empower teachers and learners, promote change and foster the development of '21st century skills, but data to support these beliefs are still limited. Some of the technologies integration used for teaching-learning are internet facilities, power point, Microsoft word, projectors e-notes, video enhanced learning software, projectors and e-mail, Google classroom app, digital classroom and smart board. There is widespread belief that Technology can and will empower teachers and learners, transforming teaching and learning processes from being highly teacher-dominated to student-centred, and that this transformation will result in increased learning gains for students, creating and allowing for opportunities for learners to develop their creativity, problem-solving abilities, informational reasoning skills, communication skills, and other higher-order thinking skills. However, there are currently very limited, unequivocally compelling data to support this belief.

Albini (2020) noted that the positive impacts of Technology use in education as given by some scholars have been proven beyond reasonable doubt. In general, and despite thousands of impact studies, the impact of Technology use on student achievement remains prudence to measure and open to much reasonable debate. Positive impacts are more likely when linked to pedagogy. It is believed that specific uses of Technology can have positive effects on student achievement when Technology are used appropriately to complement a teacher's existing pedagogical philosophies. Computer Aided Instruction' has been seen to slightly improve student performance on multiple choice, standardized testing in some areas. Computer Aided (or Assisted) Instruction (CAI), which refers generally to student self-study or tutorials on PCs, has been shown to slightly improve student test scores on some reading and math skills, although whether such improvement correlates to real improvement in student learning is debatable need for clear goals.

In spite of this, there are contending issues hampering the application of these technologies in teaching and learning. Some of which are inadequate ICT facilities, inadequate finance, inadequate computers or ICT teachers, poor power supply among others. Furthermore, another contending issue on the application of Technology is the technology or tools to be deployed and the ones to be left out. Some researchers are of the view that some Technology tools are more relevant to teaching and learning while other failed to outline the specifics in terms of Technology tool that are more to teaching and learning. For Lee (2019), e-notes, video enhanced learning software, projectors and e-mail, Google classroom app, digital classroom app are ideal for effective teaching and learning in the twenty-first century.

Statement of Problem

Teaching and learning is moving from the traditionally method to a more technological method in the educational system around the globe today through the Integration of technology. The Integration of technology in teaching is an important resource facility used in teaching and learning process which improves students' academic performance compared to the traditional methods of teaching. But these facilities are probably inadequate in most of the public senior secondary schools in Nigeria today and perhaps posing challenges in teaching and learning processes. The probably absence of these resources may result to poor learning outcomes in students, pose a threat to poor quality of teaching which may result to poor learning outcomes, and poor performances of students in CBT examination in schools etc. However, the extent of integration of technology to teaching and learning resources influence students learning outcome may have not been verifies. Thus, this research work is intended to examine the integration of technology into teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Aim and objectives of the Study

The aim and objectives of this study was to investigate the integration of technology into teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Identify the various technologies integrated into teaching and learning that enhances students academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State
2. Examine the extent of relationship between the integration of projectors in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
3. Examine the extent of relationship between the integration of power point in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

4. Examine the extent of relationship between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The study was be guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the various types of technologies integrated in teaching-learning that enhances students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
2. What is the extent of relationship between the integration of projectors in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
3. What is the extent of relationship between the integration of power point in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
4. What is the extent of relationship between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were postulated and statistically tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between the various types of technologies integrated in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant relationship between the integration of projectors in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant relationship between the integration of power point in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
- H₀₄:** There is no significant relationship between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchor on theory of diffusion of innovations by Rogers (2015). Rogers's theory stated the process by which an innovation is communicated through certain channels and over time among the members of a social system. The process will start with "knowledge" of the first channel that represents characteristics of the decision-making unit by the ICT users in order to integrate the technology. And it ends with "confirmation" by the users to accept the technology and integrate it accordingly.

Rogers went on to posit that, adoption of a new idea, behavior, or product (i.e., "innovation") does not happen simultaneously in a social system; rather it is a process whereby some people are more apt to adopt the innovation than others. Researchers have found that people who adopt an innovation early have different characteristics than people who adopt an innovation later. When promoting an innovation to a target population, it is important to understand the characteristics of the target population that will help or hinder adoption of the innovation. According to Rogers (1977) technological innovation is communicated through certain channels overtime among the members of a social system. Technological innovation refers to a scientific change or shift from the norms and everyday practice. Rogers (1977) further explained that technological innovation refers to any technical idea, practice or project perceived as being new in any social system irrespective of whether that concept has been in use a long time ago or not.

From this perspective, new ICTs such as the internet are seen to have a high degree of relative advantage, as Rogers (2001) continues: “compared to postal mail, email via the internet is faster, cheaper and quicker. Compared to books or other sources of information, the World Wide Web is a more convenient means of searching for information (that is, if an individual has access to a computer and modern)”. The Rogers diffusion of innovation theory as relates with this study shows that the recent craze for information all over the world has given rise to the opening of info-net ways thus the advocate for the adoption of ICTs into the educational system globally.

Conceptual Clarification

Concept of technology integration

Technology integration in teaching-learning entails the combination of ICT resources into the teaching and learning process. It also comprised of all electronic technologies used to store and retrieve information from various sources, generates and transfer ideas and also impart knowledge to recipients. These electronic technologies otherwise known as ICT components include computer, projector, internet services, e-learning, e-library services, flash drive and CDROM (James, (2002). In the global world today, the integration of technology has become very paramount that can fast tract the teaching and learning process.

The needs for integration of technology in teaching and learning

Anikweze and Kanu (2018) stated that the integration of technology into teaching and learning affects teaching and learning in the following ways:

- i. It provides more specific basis for designing instructions in a sequential manner and utilizing adequate instructional materials and other reinforcement strategies in the classrooms.
- ii. It makes instructions richer and more powerful in influencing learning through the application of new forms of communication in the classrooms.
- iii. It led to individualized instruction thereby enabling the learners to at their own rates through the use of programmed instruction.
- iv. It enhances teachers’ activities through the use of computers to aid their professional tasks.
- v. It provides support for student-centred and self-directed learning.

Methods

The study investigated the integration of technology into teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study adopted correlation research design. Four research questions and four null hypotheses were posed to guide the study. The population of the study was 6245. A sample size of 500 respondents from seven public tertiary institutions in Rivers State were used for the study. The sample population used for the study was 500, comprise of 300 male and 200 female lecturers. Stratified random sampling techniques was used to drawn the sample. A self-structured questionnaire titled “Artificial Intelligence in Educational Foundation Questionnaire (AIEFQ) and Students Academic Performance Questionnaire (SAPQ) with reliability coefficient of 0.82. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to answer the research questions while linear regression analysis was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The instrument consisted of two sections: Section A and B. Section A dealt with demographic information of the teachers such as gender, professional training, and years of experiences. Section B elicited information on the variables on integration of technology into teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The response pattern was 4-point modified rating scale ranging from Very High Extent (VHE)=

4points, High Extent (HE)=3points, Low Extent (LE)=2points and Very Low Extent (VLH)= 1point. The instrument was validated by two experts in department of measurement and Evaluation who ascertained the face and content validity of the instrument. A reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.82 using test-retest method. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to answered the research questions while multiple regression analysis was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance through Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

Results

Research Question One: What are the various types of technologies integrated in teaching-learning that enhances students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Responses of male and female teachers on the various types of technologies integrated in teaching-learning that enhances students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

S/N	ITEMS	male teachers N=300		Female teachers N=200		Mean Set		Decision
		Mean	STD	Mean	STD	Mean	STD	
1.	Projectors	3.10	1.14	3.05	0.95	3.014	.92	SA
2.	Power point	2.81	0.80	3.00	0.75	2.96	.96	SA
3.	Microsoft word	2.70	1.14	2.67	0.99	2.86	1.01	SA
N=500	Grand Mean Set & STD	2.87	1.02	2.90	0.89	2.94	0.96	SA

Data in table 1 show the summary of mean and standard deviation of male and female teachers on the various types of technologies integrated in teaching-learning that enhances students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State which is above the criterion mean of 2.50. This means that projectors, power point and Microsoft word as types of technologies integrated in teaching-learning enhances students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: What is the extent of relationship between the integration of projectors in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 2: Extent of the relationship between the integration of projectors in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Correlations

		PROJECTORS	STUDENTS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
PROJECTORS	Pearson Correlation	1	.924**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	500	500
STUDENTS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE	Pearson Correlation	.924**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	500	500

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows the extent of relationship between the integration of projectors in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It showed a correlation co-efficient of .924** which implies a high positive correlation between the integration of projectors in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The positive sign implies a high strong relationship between the variables. Therefore, the extent of the relationship between the integration of projectors in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Question Three: What is the extent of relationship between the integration of power point in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 3: Extent of the relationship between the integration of power point in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Correlations

		PROJECTORS POINT	STUDENTS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
POWER POINT	Pearson Correlation	1	.910**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	500	500
STUDENTS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE	Pearson Correlation	.910**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	500	500

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 shows the extent of relationship between the integration of power point in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. It showed a correlation co-efficient of .910** which implies a high positive correlation between the integration of power point in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The positive sign implies a high strong relationship between the variables. Therefore, the extent of the relationship between the integration of power point in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question Four: What is the extent of relationship between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 4: Extent of the relationship between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Correlations

		MICROSOFT WORD	STUDENTS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
MICROSOFT WORD	Pearson Correlation	1	.930**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	500	500
STUDENTS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE	Pearson Correlation	.930**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	500	500

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 shows the extent of relationship between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It showed a correlation co-efficient of .930** which implies a high positive correlation between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The positive sign implies a high strong relationship between the variables. Therefore, the extent of the relationship between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between the various types of technologies integrated in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Table 5: Model Summary for relationship between the various types of technologies integrated in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	T	P	Decision
Gender							
Male lecturers	300	39.93	7.109	410	.512	.499	Ho₁ Rejected
Female lecturers	200	39.61	7.125				

From the result presented in Table5 it is revealed that male teachers had a mean value of 39.93 (STD = 7.109), while the female teachers had a mean value of 39.61 (SD = 7.125). This result shows that the male teachers believed the various types of technologies integrated in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Further testing using independent sample t-test revealed that a t-value of .512 was obtained with a corresponding p-value of .499 which was greater than the chosen alpha value of 0.05. This result therefore indicates that there was significant relationship in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the types of technologies integrated in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between the integration of projectors in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Table 6: Model Summary for relationship between the integration of projectors in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	56502.774	1	56502.774	3504.026	.000 ^b
	Residual	9707.310	499	16.125		
	Total	66210.084	500			

The null hypothesis of no significant linear relationship between the integration of projectors in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State was rejected. This means that there was significant linear relationship between the integration of projector in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between the integration of power point in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Table 7: Model Summary for relationship between the integration of power point in teaching-learning and students’ academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	54881.881	1	54881.881	2916.517	.000 ^b
	Residual	11328.203	499	18.818		
	Total	66210.084	500			

The null hypothesis of no significant linear relationship between the integration of power point in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State was rejected. This means that there was significant linear relationship between the integration of power in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant relationship between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Table 8: Model Summary for relationship between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1					
Regression	57213.768	1	57213.768	3828.532	.000 ^b
Residual	8996.317	499	14.944		
Total	66210.084	500			

The null hypothesis of no significant linear relationship between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State was rejected. This means that there was significant linear relationship between the integration of Microsoft word in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this revealed that projectors, power point and Microsoft word technologies integrated in teaching-learning enhances students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It was revealed also that there was significant linear relationship between technological integrated in teaching-learning and students' academic performance in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. These findings corroborate with that of Chien (2020), who opined that technology is a tool for effective instructions of weak learner, who through repetitive illustrations can comprehend what they may not be able to understand at first instance in the classroom. Furthermore, Albin (2020) noted that the use of technology makes learning less passive and more interactive hence, toning up the enthusiasm of learning and passionately bring them to the corridors of knowledge. Also, Gulbahar and Guven (2019) reported that, the adoption of technology use in teaching and learning improves students' academic performance. They furthered posited technologies such as projectors, Microsoft word, power point, computers, smart board among other brings practical teaching rather than abstract teaching.

Conclusion

Technology has become an important source of innovation and improvement of efficiency for many sectors across the globe. In the education sector, particularly, the application of Technology has become a critical part of the learning process for secondary school students both outside and inside the classroom setting. Technology is considered as effective learning facilitators. The adoption technology into teaching-learning have recorded immense advancement in terms of learning outcome and improvement of teaching methods. It is, however, clear what effect the technological applications and integration have on the performance and achievement of students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should appoint digital competent management staff.
2. Management of public tertiary institutions should provide adequate technological infrastructure in the schools.
3. Management of tertiary institutions should ensure widespread adoption of AI tools for administrative and academic functions across institutions.

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